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Technical editors

Sinisa Berjan
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¹University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Agriculture, Bosnia and Hercegovina

²Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Spain

³Centro de Investigação em Agronomia, Alimentos, Ambiente e Paisagem (LEAF), Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

⁴SYSMAN PROGETTI & SERVIZI SRL, Italy

⁵University of Sarajevo, Faculty of Agriculture and Food Science, Bosnia and Hercegovina

⁶Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari, Italy

*Corresponding author: mihajlo.markovic@agro.unibl.org

Abstract

Project Promoting Smart Agricultural Water Management in Bosnia And Herzegovina - SMARTWATER project focuses on the promotion of smart technologies in agricultural water management in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH). The project is funded by the European Commission (EC) Twinning HORIZON 2020 program and it is coordinated by the University of Banja Luka (BiH). The project partners are: University of Sarajevo (BiH), Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari (Italy), Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spain), Instituto Superior de Agronomia (Portugal), and SYSMAN PROGETTI & SERVIZI SRL (Italy). The main objective of the project is to reinforce networking, research, science and technology cooperation capacities of the University of Banja Luka, the University of Sarajevo and other connected BiH institutions, in the field of sustainable agricultural water management. The focus is on the capacity building of the early-stage researchers through their participation in a joint MSc program, advanced training courses, summer schools and hands-on workshops on R&I funding. The project foresees a large set of joint activities promoting networking, joint experimental fields, research cooperation and the exchange of knowledge and experts. The main topics treated by the project are the application of smart technologies (cloud-based and remote sensing) in agricultural water management, the optimization of the water–energy–food nexus, climate change impacts and adaptation measures. The scope is to enhance the research and technical competency of researchers and university staff, as well as the fund rising skills for a successful participation in the European Union (EU) Research Programs. The project has started in January 2021 and will last three years. The experimental fields are established near Banja Luka and Sarajevo with the aim to start with the monitoring of maize growth under different water and nitrogen treatments. In this context, different smart technologies will be applied to optimize use of resources and promote sustainable agricultural practices. The EU partners will provide technical assistance and expertise to improve the research and innovation capacities of BiH institutions and to delineate adequate research strategies and policies for the future. A modern scientific strategy for stepping up and stimulating scientific excellence and innovation capacity will be outlined following a multi-stakeholder participatory approach.

Key words: *HORIZON 2020, Capacity Building, Early State Researchers, Agricultural Water Management, Smart Technologies.*